

INFLUENCE OF GOVERNMENT SPENDING IN EDUCATION ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS IN SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN SOKOTO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of government spendings in education on students' academic performance in senior secondary schools of Sokoto State using a survey dataset for a sample of two hundred and seventy-six (276) respondents. The study applied mean and standard deviation in analysis and the results show that government spendings on school personnel such as teachers, librarians, school resources officers, school counselors, among others helps to improve the students' academic performance. Furthermore, the results indicate that government spendings on libraries and laboratories, medical clinic, audio visual and media centers, reading centers, auditorium, computer rooms, home economic rooms and counselling rooms among others have positive impact on students' academic performance. The results also show that inadequate teaching and learning materials, inadequate and unqualified teachers, poor funding of education, indiscipline and corruption, bad governance and the social media (Facebook, WhatsApp and others) have adverse contribution to students' performance in Senior Secondary schools in Sokoto State. From the results, this study recommends that government and stakeholders in education should increase their fundings in school personnel and school facilities such as teachers, librarians, school resources officers, libraries and laboratories, medical clinic, audio visual and media centers, reading centers, computer rooms among others. The study also recommends that government in collaboration with non-governmental organizations should focus more on training and re-training of teachers, provision of instructional materials, more funding of education, enlightenments on the danger of indiscipline, corruption, bad governance and regular use of social media such as Facebook, WhatsApp among others.

Keywords: Government spending, education, students, academic performance, Sokoto

Introduction

In Nigeria, the history of educational financing can be traced back to the colonial period precisely 1882 to 1900. The financing of Education during this period was in the hands of Christian missionaries who owned and controlled schools for a long time. During this period, schools were established by these voluntary agencies and maintained through school fees paid by parents and subscription from churches and grant from missionary societies. The colonial government did not consider education as a priority until 1882. The 1882 educational ordinance made provision for financing of education through a system of grant-in-aid to schools established by the missionaries and private individuals. Notwithstanding, voluntary agencies spent more on education than did the colonial government during this period (Ayinde, 2009). Following Nigeria's independence and national development plans in the 1960s and 1980s, education sector witnessed a lot of development in terms of financing. It was a period of massive expansion of schools. It was a period of attainment of self-government by the various regional governments. It was a period when the federal and regional government had constitutional roles for educational development. Educational financing increased manifold especially with the takeover of schools by

the new federal and regional governments from missionaries and voluntary agencies. The first National development plan (1962 to 1966) which took place during this period made provision for the Federal government to be responsible for education and some institutions of higher learning. In the capital territory of Lagos; while, the regional governments had primary responsibility for education in their areas, even though the federal government continued to assist in the funding of education in the regions (Ayinde, 2009).

During the second National Development Plan (1970 to 1974) capital expenditure on education was £49.122 million. Out of this amount, £5.5 million was spent on Federal government secondary schools and allied services. £1.5million was given to Northern states as financial assistance for secondary school expansion while no grant was given to the western and eastern states which were considered to be educationally advantaged states. The period between 1981 to 2003 was a period of educational expansion. The public finance of education increased phenomenally. It was a period when government was solely responsible for financing education (Dauda, 2011).

However, the federal government education expenditure begins to decline from 2000 to date. In 2012, the education

sector received 9.6 % of the total budget; in 2013 it stood at 10.15%; in 2014, 10.54%; in 2015, 10.28%; in 2016, 7.92% in 2017; 7.4% in 2018; 7.04% in 2019; and 6.7% in 2020. The share of education in 2021 Budget of the Federal government was lowest when measured as a percentage of total spending Plan. Out of 13.08 trillion, 742.5 billion was allocated to education precisely (5.6%) of the total Budget. Breakdown shows that 579.7 billion was for personnel cost; 35.4 billion was for overhead cost, while 127.3 billion was dedicated to capital expenditure. The Headquarters of Federal Ministry of Education was allocated 65.3 billion and UBEC which supervised education at Basic Education level got 77.6 billion. All these shares are far below the UNESCO recommendation of 20% to education sector (Federal Ministry of Finance (FMF), 2020).

At the states level, various state government have their various annual expenditure on education sector. In Sokoto State for example, the state government expenditure on education in 2019 stood at 47.46 billion representing 27.9% of the total budget. Also, in the year 2020 the state government allocated a total amount of 47.8 billion representing 24% of the total budget. Moreover, in the last two decades Sokoto state government has shouldered the payment of WAEC and NECO fees in

addition to the purchase of reading and writing materials for senior secondary school students in the state in order to motivate them, support their retention in school and relieve their parents of such financial responsibility.

On the academic performance of students in Sokoto state, it has been reported that, the state was among the bottom ten (10) states in terms of poor performance of the students in West African Examination Council conducted in 2019. This shows that, despite the huge amount of money that are being channeled to the education sector, the poor performance of students persists. The Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education, Sokoto (2020) attributes the poor performance of the students to factors such as inadequate funding, low civil society interest and involvement in the education sector, dearth of effective monitoring and evaluation units, poverty and ignorance. Others include rapid population growth, inadequate qualified teachers, dilapidated infrastructures, inadequate teaching and learning materials, weak quality control among others.

Empirically, relevant studies had been conducted by Munda and Odebere (2014) in Kenya, Ngene and Garba (2014) in Kaduna, Dauda (2011) in Nigeria, Lawal and Abdulkadir (2011) in Nigeria and Dang and Bulus (2015) in

Nasarawa. But, to the best knowledge of the researchers, there is no empirical studies conducted specifically in Sokoto state on the impact of government educational spending on students' academic performance. It is on the basis of the foregoing that this study sought to fill in the research gap by examining the influence of government educational spending on the academic performance of Senior Secondary Schools Students in Sokoto State.

To achieve the objective, this study is divided into five sections including this introduction as the first section. Section two deals with theoretical frameworks and literature review, section three comprises data and methodology, section four and five contains results and discussions, as well as conclusion and recommendations respectively.

Literature Review

Theoretically, there are many strands of theories that explain the impact of public financing on economic activities. These theories are Samuelson's Pure theory, Peacock and Wiseman theory, Musgrave and Rostow theory of public expenditure growth and the Wagner's law of increasing state activity. But the theory that underpin this study is the Wagner's law of increasing state activity. According to this theory, there is

functional relationship between increase in government spending and the growth of an economy. This implies that an increase in government spending in education sector will lead to increase in students' academic performance.

Empirically, there are relevant studies that explored the relationship between government educational financing and academic performance of students (see Dauda, 2011; Munda & Odebero, 2014; Ngene, & Garba, 2014; Dang & Bulus, 2015; Mukherjee & Sikdar, 2012). For instance, Dauda (2011) investigated the relationship between public educational spending and school outcomes in Nigeria. He applied vector autoregressive model and found that public spending on education had significant positive impact on schooling outcomes. Also, Munda and Odebero (2014) investigated the effect of educational cost on student academic performance in Bungoma county secondary schools, Kenya. They used a survey dataset and found a significant positive nexus between unit cost and academic performance.

In additional development, Ngene and Garba (2014) analyzed the relationship between students' financial strength and academic performance in Kaduna State Polytechnic. By applying survey dataset for 320 students, they found that financial adequacy has

significant positive impact on students' academic performance. Furthermore, Dang and Bulus (2015) contributed to the topic by examining the influence of finance on the academic performance of secondary school students in Akwanga, Nasarawa state, Nigeria. They used a sample of 115 students and applied Chi-square as technique of data analysis. Their results suggest that financial status has a significant positive impact on students' academic performance.

Mukherjee and Sikdar (2012) conducted research on the impact of public expenditure on education in India using an annual dataset from 2002 to 2012. The main objective of this study was to provide a comprehensive assessment of the allocations made by the government of India. The authors used 11th Plan Period budget allocation in education which started from 2002 to 2012. They disclosed that there were insufficient financial structure and lack of coherent strategies in the plan. On the basis of their findings, the authors recommended the need for government to divide education budget into five broad components; elementary, secondary, university or higher learning, technical education and adult education for effective utilization and management in the sector.

Hinchliffe (2002) conducted a study on public expenditure on education

in Nigeria. The author used primary data in the analysis and the study covered the 36 States of the federation. The major findings of the study were lack of teaching materials, lack of information on funds allocation, distributions and spending process of financial resources in the schools and there were differences across the states between the local governments within the states especially in the financial burden of primary schools. On the other hand, Ayinde (2009) sought to determine the extent to which Adult and Non-Formal Education is financed in Nigeria. The main objective of the study was to examine the areas and problems of funding adult and non-formal education programmes in Ondo State Nigeria. He used survey dataset for a sample of 325 respondents from government's agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and private organizations. The results suggest that there was inadequate funding of adult and non-formal education from the State Government; and that adult and non-formal education agencies in the State generated their funds from other sources, such as non-governmental organizations (NGO's), foundations and private organizations.

Ebirim and Chuke (2009) examined the mode and level of funding of adult and non-formal education in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study

administered questionnaires to one hundred and twenty (120) respondents comprising of students and teachers who were randomly selected via the use of simple random sampling technique. The study found that there were insufficient funding of adult and non-formal education and that funds used in funding adult and non-formal education programmes were generated from non-governmental organization (NGOs). The study also discovered that there was no political will from the government to solve challenges confronting adult and non-formal education in the State.

Nnamani (2014) conducted a study on Adult and Non-Formal Education in Nigeria. The study examined the means of empowering adult learners in a democratic economy. The author used secondary data from Agency for Mass Education reports submitted by the coordinators from various local governments in Enugu State. His results showed that Enugu State Government was interested in the improvement of the life styles of their citizens through the provision of education but the lack of funding and inadequate facilities was affecting the issues. The study recommended that more funds and equipment are needed to provide for the development of Adult Education Centers in the State.

Data and Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive survey research design and used primary data sourced directly from the field of study using structured questionnaire, for the analysis. The population of this study is all teachers in the sixty-three (63) senior secondary schools in Sokoto state. According to Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education Sokoto, there are 1,316 teachers of which 976 are male and 340 are female.

The sample size of the senior secondary schools' teachers and senior secondary schools across the state are 322 and 55 respectively. The samples were computed with margin error of 5% and confidence level of 95% using sample size calculator published by Review Applications in 2018. Moreover, simple random sampling technique was used to identify the respondents. In the process, this study collected data from three senatorial zones of the state. In Sokoto Central, a total number of nineteen (19) schools were visited to collect data from 108 teachers. While in Sokoto East and Sokoto West senatorial zones, a total number of eighteen (18) schools each were visited to collect candid views of 107 teachers each. However, the data gathered for this study was analyzed using descriptive analysis in form of mean and standard deviation.

Results and Discussions

This section analyzed and interpreted the survey data collected. The data collected was summarized and reported in form of tables of Mean and Standard Deviation based on research questions and objectives. A total number of three hundred and twenty-two (322) questionnaires were administered to teachers in senior secondary schools of Sokoto State. However, two hundred and seventy-six (276) of the questionnaires were retrieved from the respondents while forty-six (46) were missing. This represents 14.3% of the total questionnaires. This also implies that there was about 85.7% response rate from the respondents and evidenced to be adequate for making general inferences for the study. However, the decision meant that any mean score less than or equal to 1.5, was considered as “NO” while any mean score greater than 1.5, was regarded as “YES”. Thus, the results are summarized and reported in Tables 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3.

Research Question One: Do government spendings on school personnel improve students’ academic performance in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State? The answers to the foregoing research question are presented in Table 4.1:

Table 4.1: Government spendings on school personnel and students’ academic performance

S/N	Do government spendings on the following school personnel have positive influence on students’ academic performance?	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1.	Teachers	2.00	0.00	Yes
2.	Librarians	1.70	0.45	Yes
3.	School Resource officers	1.56	0.50	Yes
4.	Counselors	1.69	0.45	Yes
5.	Sworn Law Enforcement Officers	1.20	0.40	No
6.	Nurses	1.39	0.49	No
7.	Social Workers	1.39	0.49	No
8.	Psychologists	1.60	0.49	Yes
9.	Other Supporting Staff	1.90	0.29	Yes
Cumulative Mean		1.60		
Decision Mean		1.50		

Source: Field Data (2022.)

Table 4.1 reveals that majority of the respondents accepted that government spendings on school personnel improve students’ academic performance in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. This is reflected in the fact that the decision mean (1.50) is less than the cumulative mean (1.60). This implies that the respondents accepted that government spendings on teachers, librarians, school resources officers, school counselors, psychologists and other supporting staff such as cleaners helps to improve the students’ academic performance positively. However, it rejected that government spendings on law enforcement officers, nurses and social workers have favorable influence on students’ academic performance in the

State. The finding is in conformity with the works of Dauda (2011); Munda and Odebero (2014), Ngene, and Garba (2014), Dang and Bulus (2015) and Mukherjee and Sikdar (2012) who found that government spendings on education have significant positive influence on students' performance.

Question Two: Do government spendings on school facilities increase students' academic performance in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State? The responses are summarized and presented in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Government spendings on school facilities and students' academic performance

S/N	Do government spendings on the following school facilities have positive effect on students' academic performance?	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1.	Libraries and Laboratories	2.00	0.00	Yes
2.	Medical clinic	1.80	0.40	Yes
3.	Audio visual and media center	2.00	0.00	Yes
4.	Reading center	1.90	0.29	Yes
5.	Auditorium	1.60	0.49	Yes
6.	Computer Rooms	1.90	0.29	Yes
7.	Industrial workshop area	1.30	0.45	No
8.	Home Economic Room	1.80	0.40	Yes
9.	Counselling Room and others	1.80	0.40	Yes
Cumulative Mean		1.79		
Decision Mean		1.50		

Source: Field Data (2022.)

Table 4.2 indicates that a large number of respondents believed that government spendings on school facilities have

positive influence on students' academic performance in Senior Secondary Schools in Sokoto State. This is due to the fact that the calculated mean (1.79) is greater than the decision mean (1.50). Thus, the results suggest that government spendings on libraries and laboratories, medical clinic, audio visual and media centers, reading centers, auditorium, computer rooms, home economic rooms and counselling rooms among others have significant positive influence on students' academic performance. Nevertheless, the finding also indicated that government spendings on industrial workshop area have no significant effect on students' academic performance as indicated by the respondents. These findings agree with the findings of Dauda (2011); Munda and Odebero (2014), Ngene, and Garba (2014) and Dang and Bulus (2015).

Question three: Do other factors such as inadequate teaching and learning materials, indiscipline and corruption, social media, bad governance and so on have adverse effect on students' academic performance? The results are summarized and reported in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Other factors affecting students' academic performance

S/N	Do you think the following factors have negative contributions to students' academic performance?	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1.	Inadequate teaching and learning materials	2.00	0.00	Yes
2.	Inadequate and unqualified teachers	2.00	0.00	Yes
3.	Poor funding of education	2.00	0.00	Yes
4.	Indiscipline and corruption	1.59	0.49	Yes
5.	Bad governance	1.69	0.46	Yes
6.	Social media such as Facebook, WhatsApp and others	1.79	0.40	Yes
Cumulative Mean		1.85		
Decision Mean		1.50		

Source: Field Data (2022.)

The results in Table 4.3 show that inadequate teaching and learning materials, inadequate and unqualified teachers, poor funding of education, indiscipline and corruption, bad governance and social media (Facebook, WhatsApp and others) contributed to the adverse or negative performance of students in Senior Secondary schools in Sokoto State. This is evidenced by the fact that the computed mean (1.85) of respondents of this study is greater than the decision mean (1.50). This is in line with findings of Hinchliffe (2002) who found that lack of teaching materials and lack of information on funds allocation and others are among the contributing

factors that lead to poor academic performance of students.

Conclusion and Recommendations

From the perspective of school personnel, this study concludes that government spendings on teachers, librarians, school resources officers, school counselors, psychologists and other supporting staff such as cleaners help to improve students' academic performance positively. However, this study infers also that government spendings on libraries and laboratories, medical clinic, audio visual and media centers, reading centers, auditorium, computer rooms, home economic rooms and counselling rooms among others have positive impact on students' academic performance. Finally, this study concludes that inadequate teaching and learning materials, inadequate and unqualified teachers, poor funding of education, indiscipline and corruption, bad governance and social media (Facebook, WhatsApp and others) contributed to the adverse or negative performance of students in Senior Secondary schools in Sokoto State. Based on findings, this study recommends the following: first, government and stakeholders in education should increase their fundings to school personnel such as teachers, librarians, school resources officers, school counselors, psychologists and

other supporting staff such as cleaners; second, spendings on libraries and laboratories, medical clinic, audio visual and media centers, reading centers, auditorium, computer rooms, home economic rooms and counselling rooms need to be increased by the government at all levels; finally, government in collaboration with non-governmental organization such as UNICEF should focus more on training and re-training of teachers, provision of instructional materials, more funding of education, enlightenments on the danger of indiscipline, corruption, bad governance and regular use of social media such as Facebook, WhatsApp among others by students.

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